

Ionisation Constants of some Heterocyclic Thioureas in some Mixed Solvents and at different Ionic Strengths and Temperatures

V. K. MADAN*

Q. E. Unit of CTRL (ICAR)

and

A. D. TANEJA

Department of Plant Breeding, Haryana Agricultural University, Hisar-125 004

and

V. P. KUDESIA

D. N. (P. G.) College, Meerut

Manuscript received 2 January 1989, revised 28 September 1989, accepted 26 July 1990

Acid dissociation constants of some substituted heterocyclic thioureas have been determined potentiometrically in aqueous ethanol (75% v/v) at different ionic strengths and thermodynamic dissociation constants have been calculated from these data. Ionisation constants at fixed ionic strength (0.1 mol dm⁻³) over the temperature range (10–50°) and in different solvent-water systems have been determined. The thermodynamic parameters have been evaluated and effect of dielectric constants on dissociation constant have been discussed.

DURING the last few years, some studies on the acid-base equilibria and complex forming ability of heterocyclic substituted thioureas have been carried out¹. A survey of literature shows that very little work has been done on acid-base equilibria of pyrimidyl- and thiazolyl-substituted-thioureas. Keeping this in view and in order to throw light on the interactions of these heterocyclic substituted thioureas with different solvents, the ionisation constants of some pyrimidyl- and thiazolyl-substituted-thioureas at different ionic strengths, at different temperatures (10–50°) and in mixed solvents like dioxane-water, ethanol-water, methanol-water and acetonitrile-water mixtures have been determined. The values of free energy change (ΔG), enthalpy change (ΔH), entropy change (ΔS) and minimum pK_a (pK_m) at temperature θ have also been calculated for these compounds.

Substituted-aminopyrimidines

Substituted-pyrimidyl-
thioureas
(1–6)

- 1; R = C₂H₅, R₁ = H, R₂ = H (C₇H₁₀N₄S)
- 2; R = CH₂-C₆H₅, R₁ = H, R₂ = H (C₁₂H₁₂N₄S)
- 3; R = C₆H₄-CH₃-*p*, R₁ = H, R₂ = H (C₁₅H₁₁N₄S)
- 4; R = C₂H₅, R₁ = OH, R₂ = CH₃ (C₅H₁₂N₄OS)
- 5; R = CH₂-C₆H₅, R₁ = OH, R₂ = CH₃ (C₁₃H₁₄N₄OS)
- 6; R = C₆H₄-CH₃-*p*, R₁ = OH, R₂ = CH₃ (C₁₃H₁₄N₄OS)

2-Amino-4-phenyl-thiazole Substituted-thiazolylthioureas
(7–9)

- 7; R = C₂H₅ (C₁₂H₁₃N₃S₂)
- 8; R = CH₂-C₆H₅ (C₁₇H₁₅N₃S₂)
- 9; R = C₆H₄-CH₃-*p* (C₁₇H₁₅N₃S₂)

Experimental

All chemicals used were of G.R. grade (E. Merck or Sarabhai Merck). *N*-Ethyl- (1), *N*-benzyl- (2) and *N*-*p*-tolyl-*N'*-2-(pyrimidyl)thiourea (3); *N*-ethyl- (4), *N*-benzyl- (5) and *N*-*p*-tolyl-*N'*-2-(4-hydroxy-6-methyl-pyrimidyl)thiourea (6); *N*-ethyl- (7), *N*-benzyl- (8) and *N*-*p*-tolyl-*N'*-2-(4-phenylthiazolyl)thiourea (9) were synthesised by condensing substituted amino-pyrimidine or aminothiazole with ethyl-, benzyl- and *p*-tolyl isothiocyanates. Their structures have been established on the basis of elemental analysis and spectral studies. Ethanol, methanol, dioxane and acetonitrile were purified by the reported methods². Carbonate-free KOH was also prepared by the reported method³. NaClO₄·2H₂O (Riedel) was used for maintaining the desired ionic strength.

The pH measurements were made on a NIG 333 digital pH meter using a glass-calomel electrode assembly. The temperature was maintained within $\pm 0.1^\circ$. Readings above 13 pH were neglected in the calculations due to errors associated. Indirect

TABLE 1— pK^T , pK_m , θ , ΔS AND ΔH CALCULATED FROM HARNED'S EQUATION FOR THE THIOUREA (1-9) IN 75% (v/v) ETHANOL-WATER

Compd. no.	pK^T_I	pK^T_{II}	θ_I	θ_{II}	pK_{mI}	pK_{mII}	ΔH average (kJ mol ⁻¹)		ΔS (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	
							ΔH_I	ΔH_{II}	ΔS_I	ΔS_{II}
1	—	11.79	—	225.0	—	9.45	—	34.16	—	-103.71
2	—	11.57	—	222.5	—	9.27	—	33.71	—	-102.37
3	—	11.38	—	222.5	—	9.07	—	33.71	—	-98.65
4	9.45	11.61	200.0	222.5	7.60	9.29	29.75	33.71	-75.66	-102.90
5	9.32	11.48	202.5	225.0	7.40	9.11	30.19	34.16	-71.15	-99.07
6	9.14	11.30	205.0	215.0	7.16	9.14	30.63	32.39	-65.56	-101.07
7	10.00	11.87	222.5	230.0	7.72	9.50	33.71	35.04	-72.13	-104.75
8	9.87	11.78	217.5	222.5	7.70	9.52	32.83	33.71	-72.70	-106.64
9	9.69	11.57	215.0	220.0	7.56	9.36	32.39	33.27	-70.85	-104.25

pH titration method as described by Albert and Sarjeant³ was employed to determine the ionisation constants of these compounds. The measurements were made in 75% (v/v) ethanol-water mixture at different ionic strengths and at different temperatures (10–50°) and in mixed solvents (75%, v/v) like dioxane-water, ethanol-water, methanol-water and acetonitrile-water mixtures. Necessary correction in pH for different solvent systems were also applied⁴. The pK values were calculated using equation (1),

$$pK = pH + \log_{10} \frac{[HA] - [OH^-]}{[A^-] + [OH^-]} + F \quad (1)$$

where the terms within the brackets refer to the stoichiometric concentrations of the appropriate species and F is the activity correction term⁵. The value of pK_I in each case was calculated by picking up a point on the titration curve where less than one mole of alkali per mole of the ligand has been added. The values of pK_{II} were calculated in the region between one and two equivalent of base. Thermodynamic ionisation constant (pK_a^T) of the compounds were obtained by determining the ionisation constants at different ionic strengths (μ), viz. 0.02, 0.05, 0.10, 0.15 and 0.20 mol dm⁻³ (temperature 30°) and extrapolating the plot of pK vs ionic strength. The values of pK_I^T and pK_{II}^T thus obtained are given in Table 1. For the determination of thermodynamic parameters, the studies were carried out at 10, 20, 30, 40 and 50° and at a fixed ionic strength (0.1 mol dm⁻³). The thermodynamic parameters ΔG , ΔH and ΔS were evaluated.

Results and Discussion

From Table 1, it can be seen that the compounds 1–3 have only one ionisation constant value while the compounds 4–9 have two such values. The pK_I values of 4–6 are due to the dissociation of phenolic OH in 4-position of pyrimidyl ring. These values are very close indicating that there is not much effect of substituent present in position-1 of the side-chain on the dissociation of the phenolic group of these compounds. The pK_{II} values of the compounds 1–6 and pK_I of 7–9 are due to the dissociation of thiol group which is formed by the proton shift from the adjacent nitrogen to the thiocarbonyl group. The pK_{II} of compounds 7–9 may be due to the

dissociation of proton from NH group as these compounds attain stability by the delocalisation of π -electrons. The electronic cloud embraces the whole structure.

It was also observed that pK^T values of tolyl derivatives of these compounds are lowest indicating that these are stronger acids. This can be rationalised on the basis of electrons donor property of the substituent (R). Assuming tolyl group to be acceptor of electrons, it facilitates the release of proton by withdrawing electrons from the system $-S-C=N-$, and hence lower value of the pK was observed. Ethyl group acting as a donor, tends to destabilise the relatively charged acid anions and hence the proton liberation from the acid would be restricted and therefore pK values of ethyl derivatives are higher.

Increase in temperature leads to a decrease in pK values. This is normally observed more for acids in the range studied 10–50°. The values of ΔG are positive, indicating that the reaction is not spontaneous. The positive values of ΔH indicate that the ionisation is an endothermic process. The values of ΔS are negative showing a greater amount of order in the ionised species as compared to the undissociated acids.

The minimum pK_a (pK_m) at definite temperature θ were calculated by using the Harned equation,

$$pK_a - pK_m = C(t - \theta)^2 \quad (2)$$

or,

$$pK_a - Ct^2 = pK_m + C\theta^2 - 2C\theta t \quad (3)$$

where, $pK_a = -\log K_a$ at temperature t , pK_m is minimum pK_a value at θ° and C is a constant of the order $5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ K}^{-2}$.

Plots of $pK_I - Ct^2$ and $pK_{II} - Ct^2$ vs t for these compounds were found linear. From these plots the value of θ_I , θ_{II} , pK_{mI} and pK_{mII} have been calculated. The θ_I values decrease (Table 1) in the order, $7 > 8 > 9 > 6 > 5 > 4$, while θ_{II} value decrease in the order, $7 > 5 = 1 > 2 = 3 = 4 = 8 > 9 > 6$. These trends can not be explained easily because of the higher energies of the molecules around the temperature θ° , the normal electronic and steric considerations may not be valid. The plots of pK_I and pK_{II} vs temperature (t) are also linear in the range studied. The

ΔH value was also obtained from the value of θ and t by using equation (4),

$$\Delta H = -2.303 \times 10^{-4} RT^2 (t - \theta) \quad (4)$$

as suggested by Harned *et al.*⁷. The ΔH values at various temperatures thus obtained compare favourably with those obtained from the pK_I vs $1/T$ plots supporting Harned's assumption that $pK_I - pK_{mI}$ or $pK_{II} - pK_{mII}$ is a parabolic function of temperature at least to a first approximation.

Ionisation constants of these pyrimidyl- and thiazolyl-substituted-thioureas in different solvents of varying dielectric constant, viz. dioxane-water, ethanol-water, methanol-water and acetonitrile-water at fixed ionic strength (0.10 *M*) and at $30.0 \pm 0.1^\circ$ are recorded in Table 2. The choice of mixed solvent was due to the insolubility of these compounds in aqueous media and in other non-polar solvents. The results indicate that as the dielectric constant increases the dissociation constant increases. It can be observed (Table 2) that as the dielectric constant of the solvent increases, the degree of dissociation of a solute increases giving a high dissociation constant (K_a). Consequently, pK_a decreases showing high acidity⁸.

Among the solvents, ethanol and methanol are protic in character and can make available a proton for sharing with other atoms or molecules. The solvents selected for present studies are acidic in character. The effect of dielectric constant and that of the acidic character of solvents on dissociation constant is prominent. Water molecules are universally known to solvate hydrogen ions. From Table 2, it can be seen that all these compounds are stronger acids in acetonitrile-water media than in dioxane-water media.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF SOLVENTS ON pK VALUES OF THE THIOUREAS (1–9) AT $30.0 \pm 0.1^\circ$ AND IONIC STRENGTH = 0.10 *M*

Compd. no.	Ionisation constant	Solvent-water (75 : 25, v/v)*			
		Dioxane-water (14.2)	Ethanol-water (38.0)	Methanol-water (45.0)	Acetonitrile-water
1	pK_{II}	12.02	11.39	10.80	10.50
2	pK_{II}	11.80	11.17	10.57	10.26
3	pK_{II}	11.65	10.98	10.40	10.11
4	pK_I	9.77	9.07	8.62	8.33
	pK_{II}	11.85	11.21	10.60	10.30
5	pK_I	9.66	8.94	8.48	8.18
	pK_{II}	11.67	11.06	10.45	10.14
6	pK_I	9.45	8.73	8.28	7.98
	pK_{II}	11.50	10.91	10.30	10.00
7	pK_I	10.34	9.62	9.18	8.85
	pK_{II}	12.18	11.54	11.00	10.63
8	pK_I	10.21	9.50	9.05	8.72
	pK_{II}	12.06	11.43	10.88	10.54
9	pK_I	10.02	9.31	8.85	8.50
	pK_{II}	11.85	11.21	10.66	10.31

*Figures in parenthesis are dielectric constant of solvent-water media.

References

1. J. D. GAUBA, A. D. TANEJA and J. S. TYAGI, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Fr.*, 1988, **1**, 25; O. P. KHURANA, Ph.D. Thesis, Meerut University, 1980; J. D. GAUBA, A. D. TANEJA and J. S. TYAGI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1985, **24**, 138; P. S. MITTAL, A. D. TANEJA and N. KUMAR, *Indian J. Env. Agric.*, 1988, **3**, 185.
2. A. I. VOGAL, "Practical Organic Chemistry", 3rd. ed., Longmans, London, 1962.
3. A. ALBERT and E. P. SARJEANT, "Ionisation Constants of Acids and Bases", Methuen, London, 1962.
4. S. TAKAMOTO, O. FERNANDO and H. FREISER, *Anal. Chem.*, 1965, **37**, 1249.
5. H. J. HARRIES and G. J. WRIGHT, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1969, **31**, 3149.
6. C. S. G. PRASAD, Ph.D. Thesis, B.I.T.S., Pilani, 1973.
7. H. S. HARNED and R. W. ECHLERS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **55**, 652; H. S. HARNED and N. D. EMBREE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **56**, 1042, 1050.
8. P. K. JADHAV, T. D. MATHEWS and P. V. KAMAT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **63**, 894; S. K. CHAKRAVARTY and S. C. LAHIRI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1987, **64**, 399.